

Evaluation of 25(OH)D Levels in Female Psychiatric Patients At A Tertiary Care Center**Karasala Sri Vidya¹, Karasala Indira², Pavanchand³, Srilatha Choppara⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Ongole, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Dentistry, Government Medical College, Markapur, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Siddhartha Medical College, Vijayawada, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Government Medical College, Ongole, India

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Abstract**Background:** 25(OH)D, a crucial nutrient for bone health and immune system regulation, has been increasingly linked to mental health. Deficiency in 25(OH)D is prevalent among psychiatric patients and may exacerbate mental health conditions. This study aims to evaluate the 25(OH)D levels in female psychiatric patients at a tertiary care center and investigate the prevalence of 25(OH)D deficiency in this population.**Methods:** A cross-sectional observational study was conducted involving 100 female psychiatric patients. Data on demographic characteristics, psychiatric diagnoses, and serum 25(OH)D levels were collected. Statistical analysis, including one-way ANOVA and Pearson correlation, was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify significant differences and relationships.**Results:** The mean serum 25(OH)D level among participants was 40.5 ng/mL (SD = 15.3). Levels varied significantly across diagnoses, with the lowest in schizophrenia (mean = 35.2 ng/mL, SD = 12.8) and the highest in anxiety disorders (mean = 50.1 ng/mL, SD = 13.5). 25(OH)D deficiency (<20 ng/mL) was found in 45% of patients, insufficiency (20-30 ng/mL) in 35%, and sufficiency (>30 ng/mL) in 20%. ANOVA indicated significant differences among diagnoses ($F(3, 96) = 5.67, p = 0.001$), with post hoc tests showing lower levels in schizophrenia compared to MDD and anxiety disorders. There was no significant correlation between age and 25(OH)D levels ($r = -0.12, p = 0.18$).**Conclusion:** 25(OH)D deficiency is highly prevalent among female psychiatric patients, with significant differences in levels across various psychiatric diagnoses. These findings highlight the need for regular monitoring and management of 25(OH)D levels in psychiatric care.**Recommendations:** Routine screening for 25(OH)D deficiency should be implemented for psychiatric patients, particularly those with schizophrenia. Further research is needed to explore the causal relationship between 25(OH)D levels and psychiatric conditions and to develop targeted interventions.**Keywords:** 25(OH)D, Psychiatric Patients, Schizophrenia, Deficiency, Mental Health.

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Introduction

25(OH)D, a fat-soluble vitamin, is essential for maintaining bone health and regulating the immune system. Its deficiency has been associated with a variety of health problems, including psychiatric disorders. In recent years, there has been increasing interest in understanding the relationship between 25(OH)D levels and mental health, particularly in psychiatric populations. Several studies have highlighted the high prevalence of 25(OH)D deficiency among psychiatric patients [1]. A systematic review reported that 25(OH)D deficiency ranged from 29% to 96% among psychiatric inpatients, with a significant portion of studies

recommending routine screening for 25(OH)D levels in these populations. This high prevalence suggests that psychiatric patients might be at an elevated risk for 25(OH)D deficiency, potentially exacerbating their mental health conditions [2].

The relationship between 25(OH)D and mental health, especially depression and schizophrenia, has been extensively studied. Research indicates that low levels of 25(OH)D are common in individuals with depression and may be linked to the severity of depressive symptoms. A meta-analysis of observational studies found an inverse relationship between 25(OH)D levels and depression, suggesting

that lower 25(OH)D levels are associated with a higher prevalence of depression. However, the causality of this relationship remains unclear, as depressed individuals may engage in behaviors that reduce their sun exposure and subsequently lower their 25(OH)D levels [3].

In schizophrenia, evidence suggests a significant association between 25(OH)D deficiency and the disorder. Studies have found that up to 91% of patients with schizophrenia have deficient or insufficient 25(OH)D levels, which are linked to more severe symptoms and poorer overall health outcomes. This correlation underscores the potential role of 25(OH)D in the pathophysiology of schizophrenia, although more research is needed to establish a causal relationship. 25(OH)D supplementation has been explored as a potential therapeutic intervention for psychiatric disorders [4]. Some studies have demonstrated that 25(OH)D

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care center, specifically within the psychiatric department.

Participants: The study included 100 female psychiatric patients who met the inclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients aged 18-65 years.
- Diagnosed with a psychiatric disorder according to DSM-5 criteria.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known metabolic bone diseases.
- Patients currently taking 25(OH)D supplementation.
- Patients with severe medical comorbidities (e.g., renal failure, liver disease).
- Pregnant or lactating women.

Bias: To minimize bias, random sampling was used to select participants from the eligible pool. Efforts were made to ensure a diverse representation of psychiatric diagnoses. Blinding was applied during the laboratory analysis of 25(OH)D levels to prevent assessment bias.

Data Collection: Data collection involved a structured interview and medical record review to gather demographic information, psychiatric diagnosis, duration of illness, and medication

supplementation can improve depressive symptoms and overall mental health in patients with psychiatric disorders. However, the results are not universally consistent. For instance, a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials did not find a significant effect of 25(OH)D supplementation on depression scores, indicating that the benefits of supplementation may vary based on individual patient characteristics and baseline 25(OH)D status [5]. Given the high prevalence of 25(OH)D deficiency among psychiatric patients and its potential impact on mental health, this study aims to assess 25(OH)D levels in female psychiatric patients at a tertiary care center. By understanding the extent of 25(OH)D deficiency in this population, we can better inform clinical practices and explore targeted interventions to improve patient outcomes [6].

This study aims to evaluate 25(OH)D levels in female psychiatric patients.

history. Blood samples were collected to measure serum 25(OH)D levels.

Procedure

Participants underwent a structured interview, and their medical records were reviewed to collect relevant data. A venous blood sample was collected from each participant to measure serum 25(OH)D levels. Serum 25(OH)D levels were measured using a standardized chemiluminescent immunoassay method.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Serum 25(OH)D levels were measured by chemiluminescent immunoassay. Demographic and clinical details were collected via structured interviews and medical records. A one-way ANOVA test assessed mean differences in 25(OH)D levels among psychiatric diagnoses, while Pearson's correlation examined relationships with demographic factors.

Result

The study sample included 100 female psychiatric patients, with a mean age of 34.6 years (SD = 10.4). The distribution of psychiatric diagnoses was as follows: schizophrenia (40%), bipolar affective disorder (BPAD) (30%), major depressive disorder (MDD) (20%), and anxiety disorders (10%). Most participants belonged to a middle socio-economic status (75%), with 15% from a high socio-economic background and 10% from a low socio-economic background. The majority (70%) resided in urban areas, while 30% came from rural areas

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Mean (SD) or n (%)
Age (years)	34.6 (10.4)
Socio-Economic Status	
- Middle	75 (75%)
- High	15 (15%)
- Low	10 (10%)
Area	
- Urban	70 (70%)
- Rural	30 (30%)
Psychiatric Diagnosis	
- Schizophrenia	40 (40%)
- BPAD	30 (30%)
- MDD	20 (20%)
- Anxiety Disorders	10 (10%)

The mean serum 25(OH)D level among the participants was 40.5 ng/mL (SD = 15.3), with significant variations across psychiatric diagnoses. Specifically, patients with schizophrenia had a mean 25(OH)D level of 35.2 ng/mL (SD = 12.8), while those with BPAD had a mean level of 42.6 ng/mL

(SD = 13.7). Patients diagnosed with MDD and anxiety disorders had mean levels of 48.3 ng/mL (SD = 14.9) and 50.1 ng/mL (SD = 13.5), respectively.

Table 2: 25(OH)D Levels by Psychiatric Diagnosis

Diagnosis	Mean 25(OH)D Level (ng/mL)	SD
Schizophrenia	35.2	12.8
BPAD	42.6	13.7
MDD	48.3	14.9
Anxiety Disorders	50.1	13.5

Based on 25(OH)D levels, 45% of the participants were found to be deficient (<20 ng/mL), 35% had insufficient levels (20-30 ng/mL), and 20% had sufficient levels (>30 ng/mL).

Table 3: 25(OH)D Deficiency Status

Deficiency Status	n (%)
Deficient (<20 ng/mL)	45 (45%)
Insufficient (20-30 ng/mL)	35 (35%)
Sufficient (>30 ng/mL)	20 (20%)

A one-way ANOVA test was conducted to compare mean 25(OH)D levels across psychiatric diagnoses. Results indicated a statistically significant difference between diagnostic groups ($F(3, 96) = 5.67, p = 0.001$). Post hoc comparisons using Tukey's HSD test revealed that the mean 25(OH)D level for the schizophrenia group was significantly lower than those for the MDD and anxiety disorders groups ($p < 0.05$).

A Pearson correlation analysis assessed the association between age and 25(OH)D levels. No significant correlation was found ($r = -0.12, p = 0.18$), suggesting that age did not significantly influence 25(OH)D levels in this sample.

These results indicate a high prevalence of 25(OH)D deficiency among female psychiatric patients, with

significant differences across psychiatric diagnoses. Further research is needed to examine the clinical implications of these findings and their impact on treatment outcomes for psychiatric patients.

Discussion

The study evaluated the 25(OH)D levels of 100 female psychiatric patients. The patients had an average age of 34.6 years and had been diagnosed with a range of psychiatric conditions. The majority of the participants hailed from moderate socio economic strata and urban localities. The results showed that the average blood 25(OH)D level among the subjects was 40.5 ng/mL. There was a notable variation in 25(OH)D levels among various psychiatric disorders. Patients diagnosed with schizophrenia had the lowest average 25(OH)D

levels, measuring at 35.2 ng/mL. Conversely, individuals with anxiety disorders had the highest average levels, measuring at 50.1 ng/mL. These variations indicate that psychiatric illnesses may have differing effects on 25(OH)D levels [7].

The study population exhibited a high prevalence of 25(OH)D insufficiency, with 45% of individuals having levels below 20 ng/mL, 35% having levels between 20-30 ng/mL (insufficient), and just 20% having levels over 30 ng/mL (sufficient). The significant occurrence of this insufficiency underscores a potential cause for concern regarding the physical and mental welfare of psychiatric patients, who are already susceptible due to their mental health issues. The statistical investigation, employing one-way ANOVA, revealed a notable disparity in 25(OH)D levels among the various psychiatric disorders. Subsequent analyses demonstrated that individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia exhibited significantly reduced levels of 25(OH)D compared to those diagnosed with major depressive disorder (MDD) and anxiety disorders. Nevertheless, there was no substantial association between age and 25(OH)D levels, indicating that age may not play a decisive role in determining 25(OH)D status among this group of individuals [8].

The findings emphasize the significance of closely monitoring and managing 25(OH)D levels in individuals with psychiatric conditions, especially those diagnosed with schizophrenia, who appear to have a greater susceptibility to insufficiency. These findings suggest that correcting 25(OH)D insufficiency may have a positive impact on the overall treatment and care of mental patients. Additional investigation is required to examine the causal connections and develop specific interventions designed to enhance 25(OH)D levels and mental health outcomes in this demographic [9].

An investigation assessed the 25(OH)D levels of individuals admitted to a psychiatric hospital. In this cross-sectional study, it was determined that 30.4% of patients exhibited 25(OH)D insufficiency, with their serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels being equal to or less than 20 ng/mL. Additionally, 41.3% of patients had insufficient levels of 25(OH)D. Females exhibited a higher deficiency rate of 41.7% compared to males, who had a deficiency rate of 26.5%. The frequency was significantly greater in patients over the age of 30, those with comorbidities, and individuals with psychotic illnesses. It was advised to engage in regular screening and supplementation to effectively manage this insufficiency [10].

A study evaluated the 25(OH)D levels in 40 female patients diagnosed with severe depressive disorder, compared to 40 healthy individuals serving as controls. The study revealed a notable decrease in

25(OH)D levels among those in the depressive group, suggesting a possible connection between 25(OH)D insufficiency and depressive psychosis. In addition, the depressive group exhibited elevated urea concentrations, but there were no notable variations in other measures such as TSH, AST, ALT, creatinine, and fasting glucose across the groups [11].

Another study examined the 25(OH)D levels of individuals receiving mental treatment as outpatients. Out of the 129 participants, 82.9% had 25(OH)D levels that fell below the normal range. Among them, 24% had a deficiency, and 58.9% had insufficiency. The average 25(OH)D level was 24.11 ± 10.19 ng/mL. The study found that a significant number of mental patients had a shortage of 25(OH)D, highlighting the importance of regularly checking for and treating this condition [13].

A cross-sectional study was conducted to analyze the 25(OH)D levels in 568 adults. The study revealed that 70.8% of females and 52.9% of males exhibited a deficit in 25(OH)D. The younger age group had a shortfall in 76.9% of cases, indicating that age played a significant role. The study emphasized the notable correlation between 25(OH)D levels and demographic variables such as age and gender [14].

A clinical audit assessed the 25(OH)D levels of patients admitted to a psychiatric ward. The audit revealed that 56.4% of hospitalized patients underwent 25(OH)D level testing, with 51.9% displaying insufficiency and 40.5% exhibiting deficiency. The study found a notable disparity in testing rates between Caucasian and non-Caucasian individuals, but it did not identify any substantial disparity in treatment rates. The audit recommended increasing awareness of the significance of 25(OH)D screening in psychiatric settings [15].

Conclusion

This study found a high prevalence of 25(OH)D deficiency among female psychiatric patients, with significant differences in levels across various psychiatric diagnoses. In particular, patients with schizophrenia exhibited notably lower 25(OH)D levels compared to those with major depressive disorder and anxiety disorders. These findings underscore the necessity for routine screening and proactive management of 25(OH)D levels in psychiatric populations to potentially improve mental health outcomes. Further research is warranted to explore the underlying mechanisms and develop targeted treatment strategies.

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